

CONTENT, PURPOSE AND TASKS OF THE SCIENCE OF PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS

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***Abstract.** Pedagogy is of great importance in the analysis of diagnostic educational efficiency, content of work, conducted pedagogical activities, and this method of work is successfully implemented in advanced educational institutions, achievements are strengthened, shortcomings and defects are corrected. based on the analysis, the main strategic directions are determined and high-level final results are obtained.*

***Keywords:** pedagogy, examination, evaluation, current control, intermediate control, final control.*

It is one of today's requirements that bachelors in the field of professional education should engage in pedagogical diagnostics in their pedagogical activities. At the core of any activity is the ultimate goal, tasks and expected results of the work done. Summarizing the results of activities, making practical conclusions - identifying failed or successful attempts, taking them into account in the next stages of the activity is called diagnostics. Pedagogical diagnostics is aimed at studying the student's mastery, learning difficulties, social and family factors affecting his learning. The diagnostic results allow for proper planning of the educational process, correction of mistakes, and psychological-pedagogical preventive measures.

One of the tasks of pedagogical diagnostics is to determine and evaluate the level of knowledge and skills of students. This determines the possibilities of moving to the next stage of learning educational materials and controls the correct choice of teaching methods and methods by the teacher. The task of supervision is related to finding optimal ways to learn learning materials [1, p.87].

It is clearly visible in the examination of students' knowledge. In the process of strengthening a new topic or checking homework, students have the opportunity to repeat the previous topic and learn information that is not clear to them.

The educational task of supervision is that students prepare lessons on time in order to be ready for examination, try to use free time productively, and learn discipline.

Testing and evaluation also help the student to independently determine his knowledge and abilities. They help to see one's own shortcomings and look for ways to eliminate them. But if the teacher is unfair in evaluating the student's knowledge, a conflict arises between the student and the teacher.

If the tasks of supervision, education and upbringing are carried out correctly, it becomes possible to develop the thinking of a person, to educate his feelings and moral qualities. This is considered a developmental task of self-control.

In pedagogy, the principles of monitoring and diagnosing students' knowledge, skills are defined. They are: impartiality, systematicity and transparency.

Impartiality consists of such requirements as diagnostic tests (assignments, questions), the scientific basis of the content of the diagnostic process, the friendly attitude of the pedagogue to all students, and the objective of assessing knowledge and skills.

Systematic control means that there is interdependence between all stages of the educational process - from the acquisition of knowledge to their initial perception and practical application. This principle means that every learner is regularly involved in diagnosis from the first days of his stay in the educational institution until the last days. In order to reliably check the knowledge and skills of the learner, it is necessary to regularly conduct supervision at certain time intervals.

Transparency means openly testing all learners according to exactly the same criteria. The rating of each student determined during the diagnostic process is public. The principle of transparency also requires the publication and motivation of grades [2, p.18].

Types, forms and methods of monitoring students' educational activities. Monitoring and evaluation of students' educational activities in each subject is carried out regularly during a quarter or half a year and is evaluated through the following types of control: 1) current control; 2) intermediate control; 3) final control.

The type of control depends on the form of educational work organization. Based on the topic, the teacher uses the following forms of control:

1) according to the public (frontal) form of control, the teacher asks students a question on a certain volume of the material, and the students give a brief answer to it. Asking like this ensures that most students can be monitored at the same time and activates the whole group. But this control cannot be used to comprehensively determine the level of students' knowledge;

2) a certain part of students is supervised according to the group form of supervision. The teacher assigns a task to a group of students, and the group completes it within a certain period of time. But other students can also participate in solving the problem.

3) the individual form of control is used to perfectly diagnose the level of knowledge and skills of each student. In this form of supervision, students are usually called to the classroom blackboard to answer:

4) the combined (combined) form of control requires combining individual control with public and group forms. This control is used in order to ask all students about large topics at the

same time, each student is given a separate task, and it is possible to check several students at the same time;

5) self-control serves to create internal feedback in the educational process and is based on psychological criteria. Its effectiveness depends on the professional skills of the teacher.

The methods of monitoring students' activities are as follows: oral examination, written examination, examination based on the performance of practical tasks, examination of homework. Oral examination. This method is one of the more common traditional methods of knowledge control and assessment. During the examination, the teacher asks the students based on the content of the topic studied, based on the question-and-answer method. This method is sometimes called the interview method. In the oral examination, the teacher divides the studied topic into separate parts and asks students questions from each of them. However, in order to develop students' speech and to have deep and solid knowledge, they can be asked to completely recall this or the previous topic [3,p.23].

Despite its widespread use and effectiveness, oral examination has some disadvantages. For example, in the process of its application: a lot of labor is spent; only 3-4 students can be tested during the lesson.

Written verification. It is one of the most effective methods of monitoring and evaluating students' knowledge, skills, and allows to evaluate their creative abilities. According to it, after the student has passed a certain subject or a certain section of the curriculum, he organizes the control and assessment of the students' knowledge [4,p.56]. Written examination is carried out with the help of control work, essay, statement, dictation, etc. In this process, a lot of work and time is spent for the teacher to familiarize himself with the completed work and check its quality. Due to the lack of direct contact between the teacher and the student, it will not be possible to observe his thinking.

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